

PAM 43.678 frag. 55 (IAA Plate 78, Frag 45) and 4Q5 (4QGen-e) frags. 2-3

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One of the unidentified Qumran Cave 4 fragments, numbered PAM 43.678 frag. 55 in DJD volume 33, and IAA Plate 78, frag. 45 in the Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library of the IAA, is a fragment of 4Q5 (4QGen^e) and should be placed immediately above 4Q5 frags. 2 and 3.

1 Identification of PAM 43.678 frag. 55

PAM 43.678 frag. 55 has not been transcribed in DJD 33, but is numbered on the photograph of PAM 43.678 in DJD 33, Plate XIX. In the DJD 33 volume the photograph of the small fragment is difficult to read because of the dark print, but the various online photographs of the fragment on the Leon Levy website provide better images. One may see the image of PAM 43.678 (photo Najib Albani, 1959) on <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-285457>, and the new infrared photo (2014 by Shai Halevi) on <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-492739>.

Very few letters on the fragment are fully preserved, but there are many partially-preserved letters most of which can be identified with certainty or probability. The most likely reading in line 2 of נהרג provides the clue for identification of the fragment. In our sources the word only occurs in Genesis 37:26. Also the other letters and traces of letters fit with the text of Genesis 37:25-26, be it that there are two orthographical differences. Thus the preserved writing on the fragment may be read as follows:

ם נכות זורי] 1
]י נהרג א 2

Since 4Q5 (4QGen^e) frags. 2 and 3 preserve sections of the text of Gen 37:27-30, one is prompted to compare the script and appearance of the fragment with those of 4Q5, and these are indeed fully compatible. Typical of the fragment and of 4Q5 is, for example, the long basestroke of the foot of *taw*. The fragment also shares with 4Q5 the form and size of the letters, the distance between the lines, the occasionally minimal space in between words, and (inasmuch as observable from photographs) the same physical appearance of the leather.

2 PAM 43.678 frag. 55 and 4Q5 frags. 2–3 (Gen 37:25-30)

On the basis of the wording of the text as preserved in the Masoretic Text, the missing parts of the lines of PAM 43.678 and of 4Q5 frags. 2-3 can be reconstructed to result in lines of similar length. The original editor of 4Q5 proposed a reading of frag. 3 line 1 which is problematic palaeographically (the proposed *resh* would require more space in the script of this manuscript) and with regard to the reconstruction of the text. I propose to read in this line the remnants of **ביא** of **ויביאו** in Gen 37:28, and to reconstruct a section divider with the Samaritan Text after verse 28. This results in a placement of all three fragments (PAM 43.678 marked in orange; 4Q5 frag. 2 in yellow, and frag. 3 in red) on a vertical axis, without, however, any physical join of the fragments.

[ישבו לאכל לחם וישאו עיניהם ויראו והנה ארחת ישמעאלים באה מגלעד]
[וגמליהם נשאי] **ם נכות זורי** [ולוט ההלכים להוריד מצרימה ²⁶ויאמר יהודה אל]
[אחיו מה בצע כ] **נהרג א** [ת אחינו וכסינו את דמו ²⁷לכו ונמכרנו לישמעאלים]
[וידנו אל תהי בו] **כי אחינו בש[ר]נו הו** [א וישמעו אחיו ²⁸ויעברו אנשים מדינים]
[סחרים וימש] **כו ויעלו את יוסף מ** [הבור וימכרו את יוסף] [לישמעאלים]
[בעשרים כסף וי] **ביא** [ו את יוס] **ף מצר** [ימה]
[²⁹וישב ראו] **בן אל ה** [בור והנה אין יוסף בבור ויקרע את בגדיו ³⁰וישב אל]
[אחיו ויאמ] **ר היל** [ד איננו ואני הנה אני בא]

3 Orthographical Variants

PAM 43.678 frag. 55 shows that the scribe of 4Q5 wrote **נכות זורי** instead of **נכאת וצרי**, the reading of the Masoretic Texts and the Samaritan Text. The Masoretic Text vocalizes **נכאת** as **נְכָאת**, but etymological quiescent *alef* preceded by /o/ is occasionally replaced in the Dead Sea Scrolls by a *waw* as mater lectionis for the /o/. More interesting is the phenomenon of the replacement of **צרי** by **זרי**. The interchange of /z/ and /s/ is not common in the Dead Sea Scrolls, but Biblical Hebrew does show the correspondence or interchange of *zayin* and *šade* especially, but not exclusively, before *resh*. See, for example, Reymond (2018:44) who provides the following pairs: **זעק/צעק, זעיר/צעיר, זרב/צרב**.

Appendix 1: Notes on 4Q5 Fragments

For some letters on the bottom right part of 4Q5 frag. 1 which have since been lost, cf. PAM 42.052. On the present museum Plate 420, 4Q5 frag. 2 is separated in two fragments, numbered frags. 4 and 11.

Appendix 2: Identification or publication of PAM 43.678 fragments

Frag. 6	4Q56. Cf. RevQ 31/114 (2019): 276–77
Frag. 8	4Q87. Cf. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5759042
Frag. 13	4Q388a F. DJD 30:215; but clearly does not belong to 4Q388a
Frag. 21	4Q388a 7* (top). DJD 30:208.
Frag. 37	4Q372 25. DJD 28: 197; but does not belong to 4Q372
Frag. 51	4Q1. DJD 33: 130–31
Frag. 55	4Q5. This note
Frag. 57	4Q51 114b. DJD 17:154.

Appendix 3: Present plates of PAM 43.678 fragments

Most PAM 43.678 fragments are still on Plate 78, though there has been some rearrangement of the fragments on the Plate. Cf. for Plate 78 in 2014: <https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-497952>. The missing fragments have apparently been transferred to other plates. In a few cases I have located them. References are to the present IAA numbering system

Frag. 13	Plate 125, frag. 17
Frag. 14	Plate 96, frag. 14 (PAM 43.691 frag. 19)
Frag. 17	Plate 94, frag. 60 (PAM 43.697 frag. 75)
Frag. 21	Plate 125, frag. 9 (top)
Frag. 37	Plate 196 (frag. # not indicated on Leon Levy website)

References and Abbreviations

DJD	Discoveries in the Judaean Desert series
DJD 33	Dana M. Pike and Andrew C. Skinner, <i>Qumran Cave 4 XXXIII Unidentified Fragments</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert XXXIII (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2001)
IAA	Israel Antiquities Authority
PAM	Palestine Archaeological Museum
RevQ	Revue de Qumrân
Reymond	<i>Intermediate Biblical Hebrew Grammar</i> (Atlanta: SBL Press, 2018).